

Connected Augmented Assembly: Cloud Based Augmented Reality Applications in Architecture

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Abstract

Current design practices rely on a set of computational tools to simulate and optimize the design in regards to questions concerning architecture, engineering, and construction. However, little progress has been made in tools related to the design and execution of a building assembly. This paper aims to present an integrated procedure that targets the assembly of complex structures. Two challenges are identified and addressed: first, the necessity of a connected design environment where multiple stakeholders can communicate, modify, and give feedback on the assembly sequence. Second, the instructions for the assembly of structures to untrained users. The suggested method is based on the Assembly Information Modeling framework, which provides a general approach to generate assembly information from CAD data and utilizes AEC cloud platforms as a base for communication and Augmented Reality devices as a Human Machine Interface. Ultimately, both cases are combined to constitute Connected Augmented Assembly, a bidirectional approach to assembly design, review, and execution.

Keywords: assembly sequence, augmented reality, assisted assembly, cloud aec, assembly information modeling.